

STUDIES IN SULPHANILAMIDES. PART II. SYNTHESIS OF SULPHANILAMIDE COMPOUNDS POSSESSING SELENO-HETEROCYCLIC RINGS

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Some sulphanilyl-2-amisoselenazoles and sulphanilyl-selenohydantoina have been synthesised for testing their potency against some experimental bacterial infections.

Ever since the discovery of the remarkable curative action of sulpha-pyridine in pneumococcal infections, the number of new sulphanilamide derivatives having heterocyclic residues at N¹ are on the increase and these include derivatives of pyridine, quinoline, acridine, thiazole, diazine, etc. It has, however, been established that out of the various hetero-sulphonamides only a few, e.g., sulphathiazole and sulphadiazine have actually been found to be very promising. It appears to be rather surprising that this line of research has not been extended to include heterocyclic systems containing elements other than nitrogen and sulphur in the rings. Selenium, the congener of sulphur in the periodic system, is known to possess very powerful antibactericidal properties but due to its pronounced and acute toxicity, its use in medicine is very limited. However, from time to time, patents have been taken on the preparation of organic selenium compounds and it has been claimed that the compound $C_6H_5 \cdot NH \cdot NH \cdot p\text{-}C_6H_4 \cdot Se \cdot C_6H_4 \cdot p\text{-}NH_2 \cdot C_6H_4 \cdot SO_3H$, prepared by the action of selenic acid on benzene-sulphanilamide, are endowed with highly efficient therapeutic properties [*cf.* U.S. Patent, Sept., 2,091,573, 1937]. It thus occurred to us worth while to undertake a thorough and systematic investigation on sulphanilamide compounds embracing cyclic ring systems of Se, Hg, As, etc., which are well known to possess therapeutic values.

In the present paper, some sulphanilamide derivatives (preliminary note published in the *Proc. Indian Sci. Cong.*, 1941, p. 89,) containing selenazole (I) and selenohydantoin (II) residues at N¹, have been studied in view of growing interest of

where X and Y = H, CH₃, C₆H₅, COOH, etc.

organo-selenium compounds in general (*cf.* *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1941, 28, 1) and the chemical resemblance of the above compounds with sulphathiazole in particular.

These compounds (I, II and III) have been prepared by following the older methods in general with only a few modifications. Thus in one case instead of the free base (II) its hydrochloride was employed due to its extreme instability under conditions

suitable for condensation with *p*-acetaminobenzenesulphonyl chloride. For the preparation of the required bases the method of Hoffmann (*Annalen*, 1889, 260, 304) was adopted with modifications which invariably effected a definite improvement of the older process.

The pharmacological examination of these compounds will be reported in due course.

EXPERIMENTAL

2-Amino-4-methylselenazole was conveniently obtained by the following modification of Hoffmann's method (*loc. cit.*).

To a solution of freshly distilled chloroacetone (9.2 g.) in absolute alcohol (30 c.c.) powdered selenourea (6.1 g.) was stirred in with good shaking. The reaction started in the cold with gradual evolution of heat and was completed by heating on the water-bath for about 2 hours. The product was then cooled, basified with strong alkali and extracted with ether. The ether extract after drying over potassium carbonate and evaporation gave a residue (9.4 g.) which crystallised from benzene-petrol mixture (charcoal) in shining yellow needles, m.p. 78-79°.

2-(p-Acetaminobenzenesulphonyl)-amino-4-methylselenazole.—Freshly crystallised *p*-acetaminobenzene-sulphonyl chloride (8.8 g.) was slowly added to a solution of 2-amino-4-methylselenazole (6 g.) in pyridine (20 c.c.) with stirring. The reaction started in the cold with evolution of heat and was finally completed by heating on a water-bath for 2 hours. The reaction product was cooled, diluted with water and made slightly alkaline with ammonia, whereby the selenazole derivative separated. The compound was first purified by dissolving in dilute sodium hydroxide solution and precipitating out with dilute acetic acid. It was then repeatedly crystallised from alcohol (charcoal), m.p. 228-29°. (Found: N, 11.68. $C_{12}H_{12}O_2N_2S_2Se$ requires N, 11.72 per cent).

2-(p-Aminobenzenesulphonyl)-amino-4-methylselenazole.—The amine of the above acetyl compound may be obtained by both acid and alkali hydrolysis.

2-(p-Acetaminobenzenesulphonyl)-amino-4-methylselenazole (3 g.) was heated with 15% hydrochloric acid solution (20 c.c.) under reflux for $\frac{1}{2}$ -hour, whereby a clear solution was obtained. The amine was isolated by neutralising the mineral acid. It was well washed with benzene and crystallised from hot alcohol (charcoal), m.p. 222-23°. (Found: N, 13.2. $C_{10}H_{11}O_2N_2S_2Se$ requires N, 13.28 per cent).

2-Amino-4-phenylselenazole was best obtained by working up as follows:

Selenourea (6.1 g.) was stirred into a cold solution of freshly prepared *o*-bromoacetophenone (9.9 g.) in alcohol (30 c.c.), which was then refluxed for one hour on the water-bath. On cooling, the solution deposited fine crystals of the hydrobromide of the base which were collected and decomposed with requisite amount of potash. The free base crystallised from hot benzene-petrol mixture as yellowish needles, m.p. 132-33°, yield 6.7 g.

2-(p-Acetaminobenzenesulphonyl)-amino-4-phenylselenazole.—The above base was converted into its acetylamino-benzenesulphonyl derivative in the usual manner in pyridine solution. The condensation, however, required heating for 5 to 6 hours at 100°. The crude acetyl compound was partly purified by dissolving in ammonia and precipitating with acetic acid. On crystallisation from hot alcohol after treatment with charcoal, it melted at 238-39°. It is insoluble in all the usual solvents. (Found: N, 9.88. $C_{17}H_{17}O_2N_2S_2Se$ requires N, 9.99 per cent).

2-(p-Aminobenzenesulphonyl)-amino-4-phenylselenazole.—The above acetyl compound was best hydrolysed with 5% alcoholic potash by refluxing for 4 hours. After removal of the solvent the product was acidified with acetic acid and the liberated amine, after reprecipitation from hydrochloric acid solutions by ammonia and a crystallisation from hot alcohol melts at 231-32°. (Found: N, 10.95. $C_{18}H_{13}O_2N_2SSe$ requires N, 11.10 per cent).

2-Amino-4-methyl-5-carboxyselenazole.—Ethyl α -chloroacetoacetate (16.6 g.), dissolved in absolute alcohol (30 c.c.), and selenourea (12.2 g.) were gradually mixed together and after the initial reaction had subsided the mixture was refluxed on the water-bath for 3 hours. On partial evaporation of alcohol under suction the hydrochloride of the base crystallised out on cooling. The free base, obtained by decomposing the salt with potash, crystallised from alcohol, as fine crystals containing two molecules of water of crystallisation (*cf.* Hoffmann, *loc. cit.*). The anhydrous base melts at 181-82° (Hoffmann gives m.p. 195°, decomp.). (Found: N, 13.55. $C_5H_6O_2N_2Se$ requires N, 13.64 per cent).

2-(p-Acetylaminobenzenesulphonyl)-amino-4-methylselenazole-5-carboxylic Acid.—The above amino acid was converted into its acetyl-sulphanilyl derivative by the usual manner by heating its pyridine solution for 3 hours at 100°. The crude product was well washed with dilute hydrochloric acid (10%), with water and with benzene (after drying). After repeated crystallisation from alcohol, the acetyl compound separated with two molecules of water of crystallisation. After drying at 120° for several hours the anhydrous compound melted at 238-39°. (Found: N, 10.37. $C_{13}H_{13}O_4N_2SSe$ requires N, 10.44 per cent).

2-(p-Aminobenzenesulphonyl)-amino-4-methylselenazole-5-carboxylic Acid.—The above acetyl compound was hydrolysed by refluxing with hydrochloric acid (18%) for $\frac{1}{2}$ hour, alcohol being added to effect a complete solution. After neutralising the product with ammonia, the separated base, m.p. 231-32°, was collected and crystallised from alcohol (charcoal). (Found: N, 11.57. $C_{11}H_{11}O_4N_2SSe$ requires N, 11.66 per cent).

Selenohydantoin.—Monochloroacetic acid (9.5 g.), dissolved in absolute alcohol (25 c.c.), was condensed with selenourea (12.3 g.) by refluxing on the water-bath for 2 hours. On cooling the solution deposited shining needles of the hydrochloride of the base. As the free base (m.p. 190°, decomp.), obtained by treatment of the salt with potash, did not keep well in air, the hydrochloride was directly used for further experiments.

2-(p-Acetylaminobenzenesulphonyl)-aminoselenohydantoin.—To a mixture of selenohydantoin hydrochloride (6 g.) and *p*-acetaminobenzene sulphochloride (7.5 g.), pyridine (25 c.c.) was gradually added and the product was heated at 105-110° for 2 hours out of contact with air. Working up in the usual way, a red solid product was obtained which crystallised from hot alcohol (charcoal), m.p. 263-64° (decomp.). (Found: N, 11.71. $C_{11}H_{11}O_4N_2SSe$ requires N, 11.66 per cent). The substance is practically insoluble in all the usual organic solvents except hot alcohol in which it is only sparingly soluble.